

MEDICAL SCIENCES

VACCINES FOR HIV PREVENTION: ACHIEVEMENTS AND PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The article discusses approaches to the development and creation of vaccines for the specific prevention of HIV infection. A retrospective analysis of created experimental vaccines has been carried out, the most important stages in the immunoprophylaxis of HIV infection have been formulated. The main directions of the latest technologies for the development of antiviral vaccines have been studied. The prospects for the creation of effective vaccines against HIV infection have been assessed. Significant factors complicating the task of creating an effective vaccine against virus of human immunodeficiency have been analyzed.

Keywords: HIV, AIDS, vaccine, immunoprophylaxis, variability, antibodies, immune response.

Introduction. In a short period of time, HIV infection covered all the continents of the globe and became a pandemic. According to official WHO data, HIV infection is registered in almost all countries of the world. About 90% of all cases of disease in the world occur among the inhabitants of Africa (more than 30 million people). In the countries of South and East Asia and South America, a much lower level of infection is observed (more than 2 million people). In Europe, Spain, Italy, and France are leading in the incidence rate, and in Eastern Europe – Russia, Ukraine, Poland, and Belarus. According to the estimations of scientists and independent experts, there are 10-100 times more people who do not yet have any signs of the disease, but are already infected with HIV, than there are identified patients.

Today, there are about 38 million people living with HIV in the world. Approximately 1.5 million new cases of infection appear annually. Antiretroviral therapy is used by 21.7 million patients with HIV infection, but the majority of patients do not have access to these drugs, and some have a very difficult time accepting such treatment, which is why they do not undergo it [1].

The aim of the work. To conduct a retrospective analysis of created experimental vaccines, to consider the most important stages in the immunoprophylaxis of HIV infection, to determine the main directions of the latest technologies for the development of antiviral vaccines, to assess the prospects for the creation of effective vaccines against HIV infection.

The problem of developing an effective vaccine against HIV infection has been facing humanity for

more than 40 years, so scientists from all advanced countries are actively working on its development. Hundreds of candidates have been tested in both great apes and humans, but a reliable vaccine for HIV prevention has not yet been created. Developing a vaccine against HIV infection is a rather difficult task. There is no unequivocal answer as to which of the immune mechanisms of protection against HIV are key. The task is complicated by the great genetic diversity of HIV, as it is characterized by a high level of mutations, which does not allow determining its structure as stable. HIV has the ability to form mechanisms of suppression and disruption of the host's immunity. Taking these features into account, creating a vaccine requires special approaches, a real genetic breakthrough.

The availability and use of antiretroviral therapy, which has already proven its effectiveness, stops the spread of HIV infection, but not as effectively as we would like. Mortality from AIDS has now decreased by only 60% since the peak of mortality in 2004 [2]. However, more than half a million people die from AIDS every year. In such a situation, the most effective measure in the medical, economic and social aspect is vaccine prophylaxis.

During the entire time of creation of HIV-1 vaccines (1987-2021), three main approaches to their development were used. Each of these approaches involved one or more clinical trials. Let's consider the most important studies.

The first works on the creation of vaccines for the prevention of HIV infection were aimed at inducing neutralizing antibodies. It was believed that neutralizing antibodies and the subsequent responses of cytotoxic T-lymphocytes associated with them provide sufficient protection against HIV-1. The AIDS VAX® vaccine manufactured by VaxGen Inc, (a biotech company from South San Francisco, USA) was the first development in this direction and passed all phases of clinical research. This vaccine was created on the basis of HIV proteins - gp 120 and gp 41 [3].

It was assumed that the vaccine induces the production of specific antibodies to one of the HIV proteins – gp 120 or gp 41, or both proteins. Thus, the access of HIV to target cells would be completely blocked. But final clinical studies did not show significant results, low levels of prophylactic protection were registered [4].

The next vaccine, developed by Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), included only internal proteins. STEP studies have been conducted in North and South America, the Caribbean, Australia and southern Africa. But when using such a phase 2b study model, induction of protective antibodies was not observed. What's more, a follow-up study confirmed that the vaccine, studied in volunteers in the STEP study, did not reduce, but rather increased, the likelihood of contracting HIV. In connection with this, this study was prematurely terminated [5].

The second approach to vaccine development was based on the introduction of a viral vector to induce the cellular link of immunity [6] in order to control post-

infectious viremia and potentially prevent HIV infection. This study ended around the same time as the STEP study [7].

A third approach was to use a heterologous prime-boost to induce humoral and cell-mediated immune responses [6]. The strategy is based on priming with a virus and a booster recombinant protein, which provides an enhanced immune response. If the latter is adequate, unique populations of memory effector T-cells are produced, which accumulate in non-lymphoid organs [8]. This approach was used in the RV 144 study, where stimulation of cellular immunity became the main focus. In clinical trials conducted in Thailand, the "vector" was a recombinant canarypox vector (ALVAC-HIV). These studies showed sufficient effectiveness of the vaccine: after 12 months, the effectiveness was 60%, and after 3.5 years - 31% [8, 9].

Already at this stage of research, it became clear that the development of an effective vaccine would probably require clinical trials among many different population groups, including those with a relatively low level of social and economic development. This study was stopped in 2009 [10].

In the future, the RV 144 vaccine was refined, and two ALVAC-HIV-1 vaccines were created on its basis - a recombinant and a two-component subunit based on the viral protein gp120. The action of these vaccines was based on the stimulation of the cellular response under conditions of natural infection.

The results of research on American volunteers showed that the effect of the vaccine extends to other subtypes of HIV. A similar regimen using HIV-1 subtype C showed potent humoral and cellular responses in a phase 1-2a trial in South Africa. However, the ALVAC-gp120 regimen used did not prevent HIV-1 infection among participants in South Africa, despite previous evidence of immunogenicity [11]. Nevertheless, the ten-year experience of clinical trials for the prophylactic use of ALVAC-HIV-1 has provided important information about the safety and immunogenicity of HIV vaccines in general [12].

The recombinant vaccine was tested in Africa on babies born to women with HIV infection. The effectiveness of the vaccine turned out to be low - the level of antibodies was minimal, and neutralizing antibodies were not formed at all. In connection with this, a decision was made to stop clinical research.

In 2019, scientists from The Scripps Research Institute and the nonprofit HIV Vaccine Research Organization (IAVI) were able to create a drug that was predicted to affect a wide range of strains of the virus. Scientists managed to find antibodies that bind to critical areas of the virus, which do not differ much in different strains. The idea was to better expose the place of binding of the virus to cells (the Env antigen with CD4 receptors), which the virus shields from the immune system, and this is what causes the active formation of antibodies against the virus.

When using this prophylactic vaccine, volunteers were observed to stimulate the formation of immune cells, which are needed to start the synthesis of antibodies against the rapidly mutating virus. The first phase of clinical trials was conducted. As a result, an immune

response was detected in 97% of participants who received the vaccine. According to the researchers, this is a serious step towards the creation of a vaccine that induces the production of broad-spectrum antibodies against HIV-1 [13].

The Johnson&Johnson company developed a vaccine called IMBOKODO. 2,600 women from five African countries took part in its tests [14]. The effectiveness of the vaccine was expected to reach 67%, but at the end of 2021, its trial was stopped due to the low effectiveness of the experimental vaccine - at the level of 25%, in the conditions of clinical trials.

In parallel with the IMBOKODO vaccine, the same company conducted clinical trials of the so-called mosaic vaccine (2019). The components of the Mosaico vaccine are identical to those of the IMBOKODO study, but additionally include a synthetic mosaic protein specific to the main strains (genes of different subtypes of HIV-1). Glycoprotein gp 140 of the HPV 1 strain was taken as an adjuvant [15, 16, 17].

The vaccination scheme is performed in the prime-boost mode, which provides powerful and stable immunity with the induction of T cells directed at vulnerable clusters of HIV, which will help to cope with the infection. Different versions of the vaccine were tested on healthy volunteers aged 18 to 50 years, not infected with HIV, from different countries (USA, Rwanda, Uganda, Thailand, South Africa). The vaccine candidate has shown 100% effectiveness in early clinical trials.

Currently, 3,800 volunteers (transgender men) from eight countries in America and Europe are participating in Mosaico's Phase III clinical trials. The vaccine is expected to affect a wide range of HIV variants. Theoretically, mosaic antigens can create a global vaccine against HIV-1 [18, 19]. The results of the Mosaico tests will be reported in 2023.

In modern conditions, the joint work of such companies as IAVI, ScrippsResearch in cooperation with the biotechnology company Moderna was aimed at the development and testing of a completely new, fourth approach to the creation of an effective HIV vaccine. The result of the development, which lasted for several decades, was the creation of an mRNA vaccine. Pre-clinical tests on mice and macaques of the experimental vaccine against HIV showed sufficient effectiveness and safety. The mRNA technology was not applied to the pandemic of the new coronavirus infection.

In September 2021, Moderna specialists began the first phase of clinical trials of two mRNA drugs against HIV infection. 56 healthy people aged 18 to 50 took part in the research. The safety of the vaccine will be checked until May 2023. This vaccine is based on matrix ribonucleic acid, which gives the body a kind of "instructions" by which cells learn to produce a fairly stable immune response that lasts for a long time, according to scientists - for years [20]. such technology can significantly speed up the development of vaccines against HIV.

About 20 HIV vaccine candidates are currently being tested. Currently, vector and mosaic vaccines are considered the most successful. It was they who

reached the most responsible stage - clinical trials on humans.

Conclusions. Previous unsuccessful attempts to develop vaccines for the prevention of HIV infection have created a huge experimental base for prospective optimization of the creation of effective vaccines based on advanced technologies of modern science.

There are a number of features that still prevent the creation of effective vaccine prevention for HIV infection: the expensive process of testing the vaccine, the lack of an ideal model of preclinical studies, ethical problems associated with clinical trials on humans, approaches to the assessment of epidemiological effectiveness, complex and not completely the studied pathogenesis of the development of AIDS in HIV-infected persons, etc.

Further discoveries in the field of studying all the features of HIV bring humanity closer to solving such a global problem as stopping the HIV pandemic, and in the future create all the prerequisites for a rapid response in the event of an emergent viral infection.

New directions in the creation and development of vaccines against HIV infection are relevant, interesting and promising, but we will be able to assess the reliable results of their use and effectiveness no earlier than in 5-10 years.

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